

Volumetric Estimation of Malonates by Oxidation with Iodine

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A procedure is described for volumetric determination of malonate ion, based on its reaction with known excess of standard iodine solution at 100° and titrating the residual iodine with a standard hypo solution. The procedure is applicable to neutral malonate solutions containing 15 to 80 mg. of malonic acid with a precision of 1% or more. The interference caused by salts of organic acids and other organic substances has also been investigated.

Cameron and McEwan (*Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 26, 176) determined malonic acid by heating it with an excess of potassium permanganate and then estimating the amount of unused oxidant. The product of the reaction is formic acid which is not further oxidised. In the present method iodine solution has been utilised as the oxidising agent.

According to Nylén (*Kgl. Norske. Videnskab. Selskabs. Skrifter*, 1938, 2, 19) under certain conditions iodine reacts with malonic acid to substitute iodine for hydrogen of CH₂ group and under other conditions the -CHI-group is reduced to CH₂ group by iodide ion and free iodine is formed. He also found that at pH < 1 practically no iodine reacted with malonic acid, but at pH > 5 an amount corresponding to the following reaction was consumed.

In the present method, neutral malonate solution is heated with a known excess of standard iodine solution for a considerable time in a flask fitted with a glass-joint water condenser to prevent iodine from escaping. One of the products of the reaction is iodoform. It is also found that for every molecule of malonic acid, 4 atoms of iodine are consumed. Knowing the amount of iodine consumed, the quantity of malonic acid present is calculated. Although the consumption of iodine is quantitative, the exact course of the reaction resulting in the formation of iodoform is not known. Further investigation in this connection is in progress.

M/10 iodine (1 c.c.) consumed = 5.2 mg. of malonic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium hydroxide, sodium thiosulphate, iodine, and starch used were of A.R. quality. Potassium iodide was of E. Merck's variety and malonic acid was of Johnson. 0.1M Iodine solution (containing 50 g. KI per litre), 0.1N and 0.05N hypo, 0.1N-NaOH, and 1% aqueous starch solutions were prepared. Standard solutions of sodium malonate were prepared by adding the calculated amount of sodium hydroxide solution to standard malonic acid solutions.

Procedure.—A neutral malonate solution, (5 to 15 c.c.) containing 15 to 80 mg. of malonic acid was pipetted into a 250 c.c. flask, a known excess (6 times) of the standard iodine solution was added, and the total volume was made 70 to 100 c.c. with distilled water. A 3 feet long water condenser with ground-glass joint was attached to the flask which was kept in an electrically operated water bath containing water at 25°. The upper end of the condenser was closed loosely by inverting over it a 50 c.c. beaker. The water bath was switched on, the time required for boiling to start was about 20 minutes; 20 minutes more were allowed after start of boiling so that the total period of heating was 40 minutes after which the flask along with the condenser was taken out of the bath and cooled. Then the condenser was thoroughly washed with a 5% KI solution so as to completely transfer the iodine particles, sticking to the condenser wall, into the flask. The residual iodine was titrated with the standard hypo solution. A blank was also carried out in a similar manner except for the addition of malonate solution; the difference between the two thio readings gave the amount of iodine consumed. The results for the evaluation of different amounts of malonates, as recorded in Table I, show that the precision of the method is 1% or more. All the estimations were carried out in duplicates. It was found in the blank experiment that the amount of iodine lost on heating in the manner described above was negligible (less than 0.1%).

TABLE I

Malonic acid	Present (mg.)	78.00	62.40	52.00	41.6	26.00	15.00
	Found mg.)	78.26	62.53	51.87	41.6	25.74	15.47
	%Error	+0.4	+0.3	-0.3	±0.0	-1.0	-1.0

Effect of change in the amount of water, in the period of heating, and in the concentration of iodine solution was also studied. The results are recorded in Tables II and III. Satisfactory results were found when 45 c.c. of water was added to 26 mg. of malonic acid in a total volume of 70 c.c.

If the total volume is less than 55 to 60 c.c., low results for malonate are obtained. In order to get accurate results, the total volume should be kept between 70 and 100 c.c. for about 25 mg. of malonic acid.

Effect of Increase in the Concentration of Iodine.—Several experiments were carried out taking different amounts of sodium malonate with a view to studying the effect of change in the amount of iodine. Accurate results were obtained when for every molecule of malonic acid 6 molecules (~) of iodine were added. If malonic acid present was 15 to 45 mg., even a larger excess (10 molecules of iodine per molecule of malonic acid) did not affect the results, but in presence of 45 to 80 mg. of malonic acid larger excess of iodine afforded higher values for malonate.

Total period of heating for 30-45 minutes proved sufficient for completion of the reaction (Table II).

Interference.—The interference caused by salts of other organic acids and organic substances has been studied and shown in Table III. Sodium formate and acetaldehyde cause profound interference and all the added iodine is consumed. Ethanol, methanol,

sodium acetate, calcium gluconate, calcium lactate, sodium tartrate, and sodium benzoate do not interfere with the present procedure.

TABLE II

Effect of increase in the period of boiling.

*M*₂₀ Malonic acid solution (5 c.c.) + 5 c.c. of *N*/10-NaOH solution + 15 c.c. of *M*₁₀ iodine solution + 60 c.c. water. Time required for boiling to start = 20 mins.

Heating time after start of boiling.	Total period of heating.	Malonic acid.		%Error.
		Present.	Found.	
10 mins.	30 mins.	26.0 mg.	25.87 mg.	-0.5
25 (recommended)	45	"	25.93	-0.3
40	60	"	26.00	±0.0
70	90	"	25.93	-0.3
100	120	"	25.87	-0.5

TABLE III

Sodium malonate solution (5 c.c.) + 15 c.c. of *M*₁₀ iodine solution + 50 c.c. water. Total volume = 70 c.c. Time heating = 40 minutes. Malonic acid added = 26.0mg.

Expt. No.	Substance added (do not interfere).	Malonic acid found.	% Error.
1.	Ethyl alcohol (0.2 g.)	26.00 mg.	±0.0
2.	Methyl alcohol "	26.00	±0.0
3.	Na-acetate "	26.26	+1.0
4.	" benzoate "	26.00	±0.0
5.	" tartrate "	26.00	±0.0
6.	Ca-gluconate "	26.26	+1.0
7.	" lactate "	26.13	+0.5
8.	" butyrate "	26.13	+0.5
9.	Benzaldehyde "	26.13	+0.5
Substances interfere.			
10.	CCl ₄ "	26.52	+2.5
11.	K-citrate "	26.91	+3.8
12.	Glucose "	29.38	+13.6
13.	Formaldehyde "	32.24	+24.0
14.	Salicylaldehyde "	37.83	+30.0
15.	Na-oxalate "	56.03	+115.5
16.	" salicylate "	55.90	+115.0
17.	" borate "	50.83	+95.5
18.	" phthalate (containing 0.2g. of acid)	27.04	+4.0
19.	" adipate "	27.69	+6.5
20.	" aminoacetate "	29.64	+14.0
21.	" phenylacetate "	26.78	+3.0
22.	" maleate "	36.92	+42.0
23.	" malate "	26.91	+3.5
24.	" fumarate "	26.34	+9.0

The present procedure is an improvement over that described by Cameron and McEwan in its precision and applicability in presence of many other organic compounds. Tartaric acid interferes with the procedure of Cameron and McEwan, whereas the present procedure is not interfered by its presence.

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